

Assessment of Axial Burnup Profiles and Control Rod Effects for Improved Burnup Credit Implementation

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ABSTRACT

Burnup Credit (BUC) is a well-established approach used to account for the Nuclear Criticality safety assessment of spent fuel assemblies, in particular Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) Uranium Oxide (UOX), to take credit of the irradiation of the fuel. In France, BUC is generally implemented through the “50 least-irradiated centimeters” approach, approved by the French nuclear safety authority in the early 1980s. Although robust, this method assumes a uniform axial burnup profile with a conservative burnup value, which can lead to unnecessarily conservative safety margins. More advanced methods would allow for the integration of detailed axial burnup profiles, resulting in more realistic and potentially less conservative assessments.

This paper presents the axial burnup profiles of fuel assemblies in a representative 900 MWe French PWR UOX core evaluated using CASMO5/SIMULATE5 code sequence. The computed profiles are compared with bounding profiles obtained from French measurements performed in La Hague reprocessing plant, and with the reference profiles published in the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 report. A methodology is proposed for determining bounding Normalized Axial Burnup Profiles (NABPs) for BUC implementation.

A complementary study considering different control rod insertion depths has been performed to assess more conservative profiles. In some cases, the burnup profiles obtained were more penalizing than those reported in NUREG/CR-6801. This emphasizes the importance of accurately characterizing the reactor core management parameters – particularly control rods insertion – when establishing bounding NABP for BUC approach.

Keywords: burnup credit, burnup, profile.

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnup Credit (BUC) is a well-established approach used for the Nuclear Criticality safety assessment of spent fuel assemblies, in particular Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) Uranium Oxide (UOX), to take credit of the irradiation of the fuel. BUC is generally implemented in France through the “50 least-irradiated centimeters” approach, which was approved by the French nuclear safety authority in the early 1980s. This method assumes a uniform Axial Burnup Profile (ABP) corresponding to the average burnup of the least-irradiated 50 cm portion of the Fuel Assembly (FA), generally located at the upper end. More advanced methods could be less penalizing, particularly by using a non-uniform ABP.

Theoretical bounding ABPs for PWR UOX are available in the literature: profiles from measurements at La Hague reprocessing plant of spent FAs from French 900 MWe PWR [1], and profiles determined using 3D-depletion calculations presented in the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 report [2].

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However, the FAs measured at La Hague plant are relatively old and cover only a limited number of assemblies. In addition, NUREG profiles are based on calculations performed in the 1990s on U.S. PWRs. Therefore, it is worthwhile to conduct studies using state-of-the-art core evolution codes and considering actual French fuel management. The purpose of this study is to determine bounding ABPs using CASMO5/SIMULATE5 code sequence (CMS) and compare them with those obtained by measurement at La Hague reprocessing plant and those from NUREG.

2. EXISTING BOUNDING AXIAL BURNUP PROFILES

A Normalized Axial Burnup Profile (NABP) represents an axial burnup profile divided by the assembly-average burnup. This normalization enables to compare FAs of different average burnups. Bounding NABPs for PWR UOX fuel have been determined from two major sources:

- French measurements database [1] based on 209 spent fuel assemblies reprocessed at La Hague plant. Bounding NABPs were determined for two burnup ranges: < 30 GWd/tU and ≥ 30 GWd/tU. However, this database contains few low-burnup assemblies: only nine below 30 GWd/tU and a single one below 18 GWd/tU.
- U.S. NRC NUREG/CR-6801 [2], based on 3,169 simulated profiles of U.S. PWRs, calculated using 3D depletion codes such as NEMO, SIMULATE-3, PRESTO-II, and ANC. The NUREG report provides bounding NABPs for three burnup ranges: < 18 GWd/tU, 18–30 GWd/tU, and > 30 GWd/tU.

These profiles are presented in *Figure 1*. An active height of 365.76 cm, representative of 900 MWe PWR, has been considered in all the plots presented hereafter.

Figure 1 : Bounding axial burnup profiles from La Hague plant measurements [1] and from NUREG [2]

3. AXIAL BURNUP PROFILES CALCULATIONS

This paper presents a study of the ABP of PWR UOX 900 MWe FAs calculated using 3D-depletion code.

3.1. Calculation tools for ABPs

Axial burnup profiles (ABPs) for 900 MWe PWR UOX fuel assemblies were calculated using CASMO5/SIMULATE5 (CMS5) code system developed by Studsvik Scandpower Inc. CASMO5 is a multi-group, 2D lattice deterministic code [3]. SIMULATE5 is a multi-group, 3D steady state nodal code for PWR and BWR analysis [4]. All calculations employed the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library. The active fuel length of each assembly was axially subdivided into 26 nodes of approximately 14 cm each.

3.2. Model description

A representative 900 MWe French PWR UOX core was modeled, with assemblies irradiated during four operating cycles. The core contains 157 UOX FAs. The enrichment of fresh UOX fuel was set to 3.7 wt.% U-235.

For reactivity control, different Rod Cluster Control Assemblies (RCCAs) banks can be inserted into the guide tubes of the FAs. The RCCAs contain a set of 24 Control Rods (CRs). The RCCAs used in this study consist in Ag-In-Cd (AIC) CRs and hafnium CRs. The regulation (R) bank, which enables the temperature regulation, consisting of AIC RCCAs, are inserted into around 30 cm on some FAs. In addition, hafnium rods are fully inserted on some FAs located at the periphery of the core to protect the reactor vessel from the neutron fluence.

3.3. Methodology for bounding NABP determination

The bounding NABP is typically characterized by the lowest burnup at the upper end of the fuel. To quantify this effect, the R50 ratio is defined as the burnup of the upper 50 cm of the assembly divided by the assembly-average burnup. A smaller value of R50 indicates a more distorted profile and is therefore more conservative from a criticality-safety point of view.

3.4. Average axial burnup profiles for each cycle

CMS5 calculations are performed until core equilibrium is reached. The average ABPs and NABPs obtained for FAs irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles are presented in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2: Average ABPs and NABPs of FAs irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles

For 1-cycle irradiated FAs, the average NABP presents significant depressions at the extremities of the active region due to axial neutron leakage in the core, leading to the more conservative profile with a minimal R50 value of 0.72. With irradiation, NABP tends to flatten due to the under-irradiation of the ends of the FAs (more fissile nuclides compared to the FA center). R50 value thus increases up to an average of 0.79 for FAs irradiated during 4-cycles.

3.5. Axial burnup profiles of all FAs

Due to the one-eighth symmetry of the modeled core and its specific loading pattern, five distinct ABPs were identified for 1-cycle burnt FAs (labelled A1-E1) and seven distinct ABPs for FAs irradiated over 2, 3, and 4 cycles (labelled A2-G2, A3-G3 and A4-G4 respectively). A2 is the continuation of A1 after the first cycle, A3 is the evolution of A2 after the second cycle, and so on. The same principle applies to the

other ABPs. F1 and G1 ABPs are identical to C1 and D1 respectively, and thus not represented. The FAs which get Regulation (R) and Hafnium (Hf) banks are given in Table I. The NABPs of all FAs obtained from CMS5 calculations are presented in *Figure 3*, along with bounding NABPs from La Hague plant measurements and NUREG/CR-6801 for the corresponding burnup range.

Table I. RCCA banks insertion history of rodded FAs in 1/8^e core modelling (R: regulation, Hf: hafnium)

Rodded FAs	1-cycle burnt FA	2-cycle burnt FA	3-cycle burnt FA		4-cycle burnt FA		
	No rodded FA	F2	F3	G3	E4	F4	G4
1 st cycle	-	no	no	no	no	no	no
2 nd cycle	-	R	R	no	no	R	no
3 rd cycle	-	-	no	R	no	no	R
4 th cycle	-	-	-		Hf	Hf	no

Figure 3: NABPs of FAs irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles compared to La Hague and NUREG

Regarding 1-cycle burnt FAs, none of them have CRs inserted. Their NABP looks similar, though C1 profile is slightly more distorted (minimum R50 value, i.e. 0.71). These profiles are less conservative than La Hague profile (R50 = 0.63) and NUREG profile (R50 = 0.43).

Regarding 2-cycles burnt FAs, F2 has R bank inserted during the second cycle. The impact of this insertion is clearly visible: F2 exhibits a significant burnup reduction in the upper 30 cm region corresponding to the control rod insertion zone, resulting in $R50 = 0.70$. However, F2 ABP is still less conservative than La Hague ($R50 = 0.63$) and NUREG profile ($R50 = 0.60$).

Regarding 3-cycles burnt FAs, F3 had R bank CRs inserted during its second cycle, and G3 during its third cycle. F3 has the lowest burnup in the upper region ($R50 = 0.74$), followed by G3 ($R50 = 0.75$). This result emphasizes the importance of CR insertion history in the ABP.

Regarding 4-cycles burnt FAs, F4 had CRs inserted during its second cycle, and G4 during its third cycle. In addition, F4 has hafnium CRs fully inserted during its fourth cycle, which prevents it from being irradiated as much as the other FAs. Thus, F4 remains the most conservative, with almost the same NABP as during the previous cycle (F3).

The bounding NABP of FAs irradiated during 3 and 4 cycles (resp. F3 and F4) have the same $R50$ as La Hague ($R50 = 0.74$) but remains less conservative than NUREG profile ($R50 = 0.67$).

4. IMPACT OF CONTROL RODS INSERTION DEPTH

The analysis of NABPs calculated with CMS5 showed that CRs insertion has a major effect on the shape of the axial burnup profile. However, the core configuration considered was theoretical and did not necessarily bound all possible core configurations and CRs insertions - for example RCCA banks used for load monitoring were not considered. As a result, none of the 1-cycle burnt FAs had CRs inserted, and the FAs irradiated during 1 and 2 cycles were less conservative than real profiles measured at La Hague plant. Therefore, an additional study has been performed with AIC RRCA banks inserted on some FAs, in particular at the beginning of their irradiation.

A parametric study was conducted considering variable insertion depths - 16, 48, and 95 cm - of an AIC RCCA bank, called variable bank (V) hereafter. The regulation (R) bank is also inserted as in the previous case. The CR insertion history of the rodded FAs used in the model is presented in Table II.

Table II. RCCA banks insertion history of rodded FAs in 1/8^e core modelling (V: variable; R: regulation)

Rodded FAs	1-cycle burnt FA	2-cycle burnt FA			3-cycle burnt FA			4-cycle burnt FA				
	D1	D2	F2	G2	D3	F3	G3	C4	D4	E4	F4	G4
1 st cycle	V	V	no	V	V	no	V	no	V	no	no	V
2 nd cycle	-	V	R	no	V	R	no	no	V	no	R	no
3 rd cycle		-			no	no	R	no	no	no	no	R
4 th cycle		-			-			V	no	Hf	Hf	no

CMS calculations are performed until core equilibrium is reached. The NABPs of the FA leading to the minimum $R50$ value for each cycle are presented in Figure 4, along with La Hague and NUREG NABPs.

For a CR insertion length of 48 cm, D1 and D2 FAs - which have variable CRs inserted throughout the entire irradiation - provide bounding NABP of FAs irradiated during 1 and 2 cycles respectively. Their NABP is much more distorted than La Hague profile. The $R50$ of D1 is comparable to that of NUREG (0.41 vs 0.43), although the burnup of NUREG profile is lower over the 50 next cm (height between 265 cm and 315 cm). Regarding D2, its NABP is more conservative than NUREG ($R50 = 0.50$ vs 0.60).

For a CR insertion of 95 cm, NABPs of FAs irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles become much more distorted than NUREG profile and thus more penalizing, with a minimum $R50$ value of 0.37 for 1-cycle burnt FAs. A comparable study of CR insertion presented in [5] using COCCINELLE 3D core code on 1300 MWe PWR led to a similar profile with a $R50$ value of 0.33, instead of 0.62 without CR insertion.

Figure 4: NABP of the penalizing FA irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles for different insertion lengths of variable banks compared to La Hague and NUREG

The insertion of CRs in the FA also affects neighboring assemblies. For instance, for a CR insertion of 95 cm, the R50 value of C1 - which is next to the rodded assembly D1 - drops from 0.71 to 0.53, as well as the R50 of B1 - next to the rodded assembly C4 - which drops from 0.74 to 0.59.

It is to be noted that R50 parameter is not entirely suitable for CR insertions of 95 cm, as the burnup of the upper 100 cm should be considered. This point is discussed in [6].

In conclusion, extreme CRs insertion scenarios can generate NABPs more penalizing than La Hague plant measurements and even NUREG profiles. Such CRs insertions are unlikely to occur over long periods of time and even less likely to occur throughout the entire cycle. Accurate knowledge of control rod insertion histories is essential when defining bounding NABPs.

5. END-EFFECT

In the previous paragraphs, the bounding NABP was defined as the profile minimizing the burnup at the upper end of the FA. This assumption holds when the reactivity is driven by the upper end of the FA. However, in some cases, especially at low burnups, the reactivity is driven by the central part of the FA, thus it is more conservative to minimize the burnup of the center of the FA, by considering a uniform profile equal to the assembly-average burnup. The "end-effect", which is the difference of the k_{eff} for a ABP and the k_{eff} for a uniform profile, characterizes this situation.

The end-effect of the FAs obtained in paragraph 3.5 for the typical core configuration was calculated for an infinite array of FAs moderated by water, with 20 cm of water at top and bottom of the active part of the FA. k -eff calculations considering ABP and uniform profile for each FA are performed with the ASNR Monte Carlo code MORET6 [7], and the nuclear data library ENDF-B/VIII.0 (statistical uncertainty σ is set to 50 pcm). For ABP configuration, the composition of the 26 axial zones of the FA were determined with CMS5. For uniform configuration, a single composition equal to the mean composition of the 26 axial zones is considered. The isotopes selected are the 12 actinides and 15 fission products generally considered in BUC [5]. The end-effect of each FA and neutron repartition in each FA at the last active step of Monte Carlo calculation are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: End-effect and axial neutron repartition for each FA irradiated during 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles

The results show that end-effect is generally negative at low burnups (less than 30 GWd/tU), which means that a uniform profile equal to the assembly-average burnup is more conservative than the best-estimate ABP. As shown in Figure 5, the reactivity is then driven by the center part - or half top part - of the FA. However, at high burnups (higher than 30 GWd/tU) the end-effect is generally positive, which means that considering a uniform profile is not conservative compared to a realistic ABP. In this case the reactivity is driven by the upper end of the FA. The transition from negative to positive end-effect at 30 GWd/tU is consistent with [5]; NUREG [2] mentions a transition between 15 and 25 GWd/tU.

It is important to highlight that this effect results from ABP being the multiplication of the NABP by the average burnup, which amplifies the effect of the under-irradiation of the upper end at high burnup. However, the NABP of lowly irradiated FAs is generally more conservative than for highly irradiated FAs, as shown in paragraph 3.3.

Therefore, these results do not allow us to verify that the bounding profile determined in paragraph 3.4 is indeed the most conservative, because the NABP should be multiplied by the same average burnup to allow for a valid comparison. This point is presented in [6].

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented ABP of 900 MWe PWR UOX FAs calculated using state-of-the-art 3D core codes, CASMO5/SIMULATE5. Based on the evaluation of the burnup of the FA upper end, bounding NABPs were determined for different burnup ranges using R50 parameter which is the ratio of the top 50 cm burnup to the average burnup. CR insertion revealed to have a major effect on the NABP.

For a core configuration typical of French 900 MWe UOX PWR, the profiles obtained for low burnups (< 30 GWd/tU) were less conservative than the recommended profiles of NUREG [2] and those derived

from La Hague plant measurements [1]. At high burnups (> 30 GWd/tU), some profiles obtained exhibit the same R50 value as La Hague bounding profile but remain less penalizing than NUREG profiles.

Since the core configuration considered in this study does not bound all possible core configurations and CR insertions - for example RCCA banks used for load monitoring were not considered - an additional study has been performed with CR inserted into some FAs from the beginning of their irradiation. Different insertion depths were considered, up to 95 cm. Continuous CR insertion of 48 cm throughout irradiation led to NABPs more penalizing than La Hague bounding profile and similar to the NUREG profile for the 18 to 30 GWd/tU burnup range.

Extreme CR insertion of 95 cm led to highly conservative NABPs, even more penalizing than NUREG profiles. However, extreme CR insertions are unlikely to occur over long periods of time and even less likely to occur throughout the entire irradiation of the FA. Therefore, the knowledge of the CR insertion history of the FAs - through the knowledge of the reactor core management data - is essential for determining a bounding NABP to be used in burn-up credit criticality safety assessment.

The burnup of the upper end of the FA has been used in this study through R50 as an indicator to determine conservative NABP. The validity of this method - comparing profiles based on their R50 value - was verified in [6] through criticality calculations considering different profiles at the same average burnup. However, it is important to remember that for low burnups, assuming a uniform profile equal to the assembly-average burnup may be more penalizing than an axial profile. For the typical core configuration considered in this paper - best-estimate ABP but not bounding - this transition occurred at around 30 GWd/tU. End-effect should therefore be calculated in criticality studies to check whether the ABP or the uniform profile is more reactive.

Finally, it would be valuable to examine NABPs for French PWRs other than 900 MWe UOX PWR, especially PWRs that use a mix of UOX and MOX fuel, as well as 1300 MWe PWRs.

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